

Further studies on varieties GMR-2 (IET2885) and Rasi (IET1444), which were in insecticidal trials, showed more than 30% incidence on some treatments. These varieties were late sown and flowered late. When the same varieties were early sown and thus flowered early, they were not at all infected. This indicates that the time of flowering has some influence on disease incidence. ■

Varietal resistance to tungro

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

Tungro virus disease first appeared in Tanjore district, Tamil Nadu, in 1978. In the 1979 thaladi season, some devastated fields of tungro-affected paddy were plowed under. The disease appears starting in the early kuruvai season and damage becomes severe in late kuruvai, samba, and thaladi. To select tungro-resistant varieties, observations were made in 3 sets (6 entries/set) of plantings made in kuruvai (6 plantings in Jun-Jul), samba (2 plantings, Oct), and thaladi (6 plantings, Oct-Nov). Among the 18 varieties (see table), TKM9 was best for kuruvai; CR1009, C025, and AD3488 for samba; and Ponni for thaladi. ■

Sources of varietal resistance to rice tungro virus. Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Rice tungro virus (%)
<i>Kuruvai</i>	
ADT31	48.4
TKM9	13.8
AS3704	26.6
PL29	22.9
AD8991	48.9
AD6120	22.1
<i>Samba</i>	
C025	10.0
CO40	63.6
NLR9672	56.1
CR1009	9.5
AD7496	54.6
AD3488	15.3
<i>Thaladi</i>	
ASD15	27.8
ADT32	30.0
ADT35	19.9
IR34	16.0
Ponni	8.2
AD9408	20.8

Fake smut and bunt diseases in IRON entries

L.P. Kauraw and S.C. Mathur, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack 6, India

In 1979 kharif, the natural incidence of false smut *Ustilaginoidea virens* Cke. (Takahashi) and bunt *Tilletia barclayana* Bref. (Sacc. & Syd.) diseases was observed in the International Rice Observational Nursery (IRON) trial at CRRI. The diseases occurred on 11 of 345 entries. The infected panicles and grains per panicle were counted from

randomly selected plants of each of the 11 entries (see table).

The maximum false smut infection (22%) was in CR1022; that of bunt (12%) was in B541B-PN-58-5-3-1. The maximum number of false smut-infected grains (1-6) was in CR1013.

Most of the entries flowered in late October. One week before and after flowering the maximum/minimum temperature was 33°/24° C; relative humidity was 88-95%, and sunshine hours, about 9-10. Rain fell on only 1 day during the period. The crop was irrigated when necessary. ■

Occurrence of false smut and bunt diseases in entries of the International Rice Observational Nursery at CRRI, Cuttack, Orissa, India.

Entry	Plant infection (%)	Infected grains (no./panicle)
False smut.		
CR1022 (Jagannath natural cross)	22	1-2
CR1016 (Waikoku/T90(40))	20	1-2
CR1013 (Jagannath natural cross)	16	1-6
IET6080 (RP894-15-2-1-1) CR44-35/W12708	16	1-3
IET6426, CRM9-3633-18, GEB24 mutant	8	1-4
IET6056 (RP894-61-1-3-7-2) CR44-35/W12708	4	1-2
IET6496 (R22-2-10.1) IRI/Sigadis	2	0-1
BW100 (H501/Sel. 306)	2	1-2
BW78-7 (H501/Sel. 306)	2	1-2
Bunt		
B541B-PN-58-5-3-1, Politai-I/IR1108-2	12	1-3
B2360-8-5-L-R-4-3, IR2180-2/IR2178-1	6	1-3

Records of heavy attack of bunt and false smut of rice

A. K. Roy, Regional Research Station, Assam Agricultural University, Diphu-782460, Assam, India

Although bunt [*Tilletia barclayana* (Bref.) Sacc. & Syd. = *Neovossia horrida* (Tak.) Padwick & Khan] and false smut [*Claviceps virens* (Cke.) Sakurai ex Nakata = *Ustilaginoidea virens* (Cke.) Tak.] are widespread diseases of

rice in Assam, they are considered minor because they affect only a few grains. With the introduction of new cultivars and application of fertilizers, occurrences of the diseases are, however, on the increase. Two unusually heavy occurrences in the Rice Experimental Station at Titabar and the surrounding areas in 1964 and 1965 are reported (Table 1, 2). The information gives the average percentage of infected grains of the infected panicles only and does not

Table 1. Infected grains due to bunt and false smut (alone or combined) on infected panicles, Assam, India, 1964.

Disease	Infected panicles (no.)	Total no. of grain	Total no. of affected grain	Affected grain (%)
Bunt	19	3608	1239	34.21
False smut	7	1298	473	36.44
Bunt + false smut	2	329	188	57.14

Table 2. Bunt- and false smut-infected grains on affected panicles of different cultivars, Assam, India, 1965.

Cultivar	Bunt-infected grain (%)	False smut-infected grain (%)
TN1	39.71	—
Unknown	22.34	—
Unknown	1.36	1.49
Unknown	26.32	0.11
Hsinchu 2	10.42	—
Unknown	—	2.01

represent the total field population (on individual panicles bunt varied from 8 to 63% and false smut, 18 to 79% in 1964). ■

Hypersensitive reaction induced by *Xanthomonas oryzae* in the cowpea leaf

K. Tsuchiya, T. W. Mew, and S. Wakimoto, Plant Pathology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Lesion development due to virulent strains of *Xanthomonas oryzae* on rice leaves was remarkably inhibited by both mixing and preinoculation treatments with an avirulent or weakly virulent mutant strain in experiments conducted at the IRRI greenhouse. But no inhibitory effect was observed when the virulent strain was inoculated before the avirulent or weakly virulent strains.

All efforts have failed to induce a hypersensitive reaction (HR) by combining a resistant rice variety and the *X. oryzae* strain. But cowpea was found to be a suitable indicator for HR induction. HR was rapidly induced by both virulent wild strains exemplified by different virulence groups and by virulent induced mutants. Only living cells of bacteria could induce HR, and critical numbers for induction seemed to be $2-5 \times 10^6$ cells/ml. None of heat-killed bacterial cells, cell-free supernatants, or polysaccharide fraction prepared from the bacterial culture induced HR. On the other hand, avirulent strains either delayed HR or did not induce it at all. ■

Resistance to bacterial blight

V. Mariappan, Valluva Paridasan, and P. Durairaj, Coimbatore, India

Rice cultivars were screened for resistance to bacterial blight disease. The plants were raised in pots containing wetland soil and in the field spaced 20 x 10 cm. Fertilizers were applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha. The plants were inoculated at three stages: seedling (20 days), tillering (50 days), and boot-leaf. The disease severity was scored on a scale of 0-9. Many cultivars were rated susceptible; a few were moderately resistant.

Interestingly, ASD5 was resistant,

Reaction of rice varieties or cultures to bacterial blight disease.

Variety or culture	Disease severity scale ^a					
	Seedling		Tillering		Boot-leaf	
	Pots	Field	Pots	Field	Pots	Field
BJ1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Sigadis	0	0	0	0	1	0
TKM6	1	0	1	0	1	1
ASD5	1	0	1	1	5	5
IR22	1	1	5	3	5	5
IR26	3	1	5	5	5	5
Pankaj	1	1	3	1	3	3
TN1	5	5	7	7	7	7
TNAU7124 (ASD5/IR22)	1	1	1	1	5	3
TNAU15776 (IR20/ASD5)	1	1	1	1	5	3
ASD15 (IR22/IR26)	3	3	7	7	7	7

^a0 = not affected, 9 = highly susceptible.

Life span of and tungro transmission by viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on 10 rice varieties at AICRIP, India

V. T. John and A. Ghosh, All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, A. P., India

To determine possible strains of tungro virus and biotypes of tungro vectors in various localities, the life span and tungro transmission of *Nephotettix virescens* collected and reared locally were tested on seedlings of 10 rice varieties in

comparable with TKM6 until tillering. IR22 and IR26 were moderately susceptible and ASD5 was resistant in the tillering stage. But ASD5 became infected in the panicle-emergence stage. Progeny of ASD5—TNAU7124 and TNAU15776 — also scored resistant until tillering and were moderately susceptible in the boot-leaf stage. The contribution of resistance by IR22 and IR20 in those two cultivars appears insufficient. ASD15 (IR22/IR26) is also susceptible (see table).

ASD5 has potential resistance until the tillering stage to the bacterium strain that causes severe damage to most of the improved rice varieties known to be bacterial-blight resistant. ■

the AICRIP greenhouse, Rajendranagar, India, 12-30 September 1978. Two hundred adult insects, 10 females and 10 males for each variety, were given an acquisition access time of 3 days on tungro-diseased plants. The insects survived 1 to 18 days on 1-week-old seedlings. Their average life span was 4.6 days (5.0 days for female insects and 4.2 days for the male).

When the average life span was used to indicate the effect of rice variety on the insect, Gam Pai 30-12-15, IR34, Ptb 18, and Ambemohar 159 showed more resistance to the insect than Habiganj

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.